

ISSN : 2349-4212

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF

TRENDS IN BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

Indexed by:

Universal
Impact Factor

IMPACT FACTOR
SEARCH

Founder and Publisher **academic journals PVT LTD**

Published science may 2011 year. Issued Quarterly.

Internet address: <http://academicjournalonline.org/index.php/ijtba>

10/25 Thamostraran Street, Arisipalayam, Salem, India

Principal Contact

Academic Journal Online

info@academicjournalonline.org

Editorial board

1. Mallesh Thumalla
2. Edwin Prem Kumar
3. Farha Deeba Hassan
4. Sangeetha T.R.
5. Abdul Wahid Naureena
6. Urokov Uchkun Yunusovich
7. Baymirzaev Dilmurod Nematovich
8. Faisal Amjad
9. Muhammad Tariq
10. Nadeem Abbas
11. Mr. Iftikhar Ahmad
12. Usmanova Muxlisa Sagdullayevna
13. Pulatova Mokhira Bakhtiyorovna
14. Sangeetha Natarajan
15. Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich

THE NOTION OF INFORMATION AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE STATE ECONOMY

Jamankulova E.F. - PhD, Associate Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service. Uzbekistan. Samarkand.

Abstract: This article highlights the notions of an informed economy, the importance of information and communication technologies in the development and development of the national economy. In our society the notion of information economy is spreading widely. Actually, in this situation one question may be appeared: what information economy is. Broadly speaking, in the scientific literature Information economy is considered as an economic trend which studies the effects of information to the decision of information economy.

Keywords: Information economy, information society, information and communication technologies.

Introduction.

Since the beginning of 90th of XX century the field of Information has developed intensively. It has become common to say that XXI century-Information and communication century. It makes everyone in our society be interested in these questions naturally that what Information is, what its tasks are, what its main peculiarities are. Because it is difficult to imagine the human activities without information.

In everyday life we have to work with various forms of information such as textual, graphical (diagram), schedule, sound(audio), illustrated(pictured),video etc. In order to work (assemble, save)with each sort of information we need an informational construction which has various technical characteristics.

The development of microelectronic producing technology and the creation of modern processor computers are enlarging opportunities to recycle information. [1,2]

Nowadays in our society the notion of information economy is spreading widely. Actually, in this situation one question may be appeared: what information economy is. Broadly speaking, in the scientific literature Information economy is considered as an economic trend which studies the effects of information to the decision of information economy. In the work “ The structure of Information” by M.A.Nikitenkiva following definition is given to this term “ Information economy – a developing stage of producing forces; It is a creation of global information field which is the knowledge and the role of information in the society’s life, people’s mutual exchanging information effectively.it would give chances for people to use

the world's information resources and a provider of the satisfaction of their social and private necessity.

As any country, in Uzbekistan else, it may project the increasing the forming degree of information economy, implementing modern information and communication technologies and a share of the service field in total internal products. In our country the development of Information and communication technologies is implemented based on the program developing branch of national information communication of the Republic of Uzbekistan outlined 2013-2020 years.

This program was confirmed in the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov's PR-1730 resolution in 2012 "About the actions of development once more and imposing modern information and communication technologies" The main purpose intending to developing information and communication technologies in our country aims to impose state programs successfully according to the development of information and communication technologies and to form information economy in it effectively. The comparative analysis of information economy among countries is implemented with depending on developing of the following tendencies.

- The difference of traditional economy and information economy
- Forming of certain opposition between information economy and the fields of economy of industry period
- Entering the global economy from day to day

The scientists M. Castels , M. Connors , U .Martin and A. Norman have conveyed the analysis of the maintenance of information economy in their scientific work. But the category of information economy was inserted to the science by M. Porat, the American economist, in 1976. Likewise the Spanish-American economist M. Castels emphasized that the term of "Information economy" is not a perfect conception, it does not reflect itself all peculiarities of the new field.

Oppositely, the conception "Information economy" has a certain characterization, it is a progressing stage of civilization that has superiority in economic labour and information riches. Therefore, this term also may be given a characterization by theoretically. Information economy is a foundation of postindustrial society, it is considered as philosophic-economic term marking the peculiarities of economy that information is a resource of main production and also in the organization of the being busy the principal place has been occupied by whom are busy with mental work. Including that in 1996-1998 the monography

“Information Age: economy, society and culture” written by M.Castels caused the term of information economy to spread widely in the society.

The forming of information economy can be separated into 3 period according to the time measure :

1. Appearing of information economy and determining the tendency of progressing of new events.(1960-1970)
2. Developing of information economy intensively in the leading countries.(1980-1990)
3. Studying the theory of information economy connection with knowledge economy.(since 2000)

Generally speaking, in the theory of economy there is not a unique definition or notion of information economy, but there are various approaches to it in scientific literature. However, in the conducted investigation information economy is divided into the group of 3 main scales.

In the first group, economy balances can be introduced ,they denote the share of the total national product which was composed in the information branch of society. The main problem of this approach is that they are considered to come across a certain difficulties in producing total national product of the country. In the second group, social balances can be shown. They determine the information products, producing the means of information and the share of people who are busy in the branch of information service. In the third group, you can see technological balance that defines the point of view of expanding the information technology that is to say to indicate information economy in society.

At this moment, Despite the Time and distance, the development of new technologies with the progress of information and communication technologies is giving a chance to exchange and deliver information, money and other resources. Also, the basis chances occurring with the tie of passing to information economy is causing several problems and conflicts. [3]

For instance, such kind of problems can be inserted the changeability and inconstancy of economic life which has appeared owing to information and globalization concerning to various fields in society and studying overall and unraveling which demands to complex approach. From them it is necessary to emphasize separately the increasing the effects of information and communication technologies and innovational, scientific and educational activities to the society, country and economy and possessing new peculiarities of their activities from the aspect of quality. [4]

That's why, It is getting more and more important task to show the individual peculiarities of information economy such as how it describes the conflicts in social life and reflects its essence by theoretical aspect in the world economy of the stage of current time. Therefore, the strategy of developing the system of National information communication which includes and implements all trends of developing information and communication technologies is performing the tendency of active positive increase. It denotes that the total portion of information economy has an influence considerably to economy.

Last short period of globalization processes, in the field of one of main active mechanization Information and communication technologies in new trends are being created corresponding to the requirement of Time. These technologies both offer much enough from classic models of computer branches and sometimes work based on just the same tendencies.

Even though the idea of nebulous calculation appeared in 1960's of previous century it has passed to the developing stage and popularized since 2007 as a result of increasing the demand of users continuously and progressing of connection channels intensively.

Conclusion.

To sum, introducing information and communication technologies widely and actively causes to increase the quantity of scientific researches in the service and producing branches of economy, rising up implementing of one branch's activity connecting with others, to the transformation of the role of information, to component unproportion in the labour market.

Sh. Mirziyoyev, The President of Republic of Uzbekistan emphasized in the video selector meeting concerning measures adjusted to shortening the poverty through developing the business work on February 27 "I have spoken about the poverty for the first time in the proclamation to the Supreme Council. We have much of them. It is obvious that, up to now we have given fish to our people. This experience has not justified itself. Then we must teach them to fish."

Taking into consideration, It means one of the most important attempts to conduct scientific researches according to solving the effect of information economy, form and develop information economy on a large scale in Uzbekistan.

References:

- [1]. Jamankulova F. (2022). CONNECTION OF BLOCKCHAINS WITH SOFTWARE SYSTEMS. ASEAN Journal on Science & Technology for Development, Vol 39(No 4), 128–131. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6480915>

- [2]. Jomonkulova E.F, & Shadmanov I.E. (2022). MODERN CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. ASEAN Journal on Science & Technology for Development, Vol 39(No 4), 106–109. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6474376>
- [3]. Jamankulova, E. F., & Nizomov, M. Q. (2020). The Notion Of Information And Its Significance In The State Economy. CUTTING EDGE-SCIENCE, 20.
- [4]. Jomonqulova, F. E., Marjona, T., & Diyora, N. (2022). ECONOMIC INFORMATION PROCESSING PROGRAMS. International journal of trends in computer science, 3(1).
- [5]. Jomonqulova F. E. et al. THE CONCEPT OF INFORMATIZATION AND ITS ROLE IN THE ECONOMY OF THE COUNTRY //Colloquium-journal.
- [6]. Kun.uz (internet resource) (not to give fish to people, fishing rod must be given them ”-President)
- [7]. Porat V. The Information Economy Definition and Measurement. Washington DC: US Dept of Commerce, 1977. P.240.